

Project acronym: SURE-Farm

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D7.2. Infographics delivered throughout the project

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1 Kick-off infographic: SURE-Farm at a glance

Issue date: 06/10/2017

Available at SURE-Farm website:

https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/SURE-Farm_First-Infographic_V4.pdf

2 SURE-Farm video presentation: What is SURE-Farm

Issue date: 05/04/2018

Available at:

- o SURE-Farm website: <https://www.surefarmproject.eu/digital-materials/>
- o Youtube SURE-Farm account: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dvK7gfSwpuY>

Subtitles translated into Bulgarian, Dutch, English, French, German, Italian, Polish, Romanian, Spanish.

3 Infographic to support the Policy Brief on Resilience Framework (D1.5)

Issue date: 04/06/2018

Available at SURE-Farm website:

https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/Infographic_Policy-brief-Resilience-Framework.png

4 GIF to support the Policy Brief on farm demographics and impacts on farm structure (D3.3)

- Issue date: 02/09/2019
- Available at SURE-Farm website:

https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/GIF_Farm-demographics.gif

- 5 GIF to support the Policy brief on farmer adaptive behaviour and risk management in EU agriculture (D2.5).

- Issue date: 23/09/2019
- Available at SURE-Farm website:

https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/GIF_2.5-Policy-Brief-on-Risk-Management.gif

- 6 Infographic to support the business brief on opportunities for improved risk management for EU agriculture (D2.7).

- Issue date: 11/12/2019
- Available at SURE-Farm website:

https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/Business-Brief-on-improved-risk-management_Infographic-scaled.jpg

- 7 Infographic to support the Policy brief on future farm demographics and structural change in selected regions of the EU (D3.6).

- 🍃 Issue date: 01/04/2020
- 🍃 Available at SURE-Farm website:

<https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Infographic-Farm-Demographics-scaled.jpg>

- 8 Infographic to support the Business Brief on shifting the focus from “more” to “more successful” generational renewal (D3.7)

Six questions to shifting the focus from more to more successful generational renewal in farming

<p>2 IS A LACK OF SUCCESSORS OF FAMILY FARMS A KEY CONCERN FOR THE RESILIENCE OF FARMING SYSTEMS?</p> <p>More focus ought to be placed on the quality of succession rather than the quantity of successors.</p>	
<p>4 WHAT IS IMPORTANT FOR THE FARM TRANSFER PROCESS?</p> <p>Farm succession benefits greatly from timely and open communication and planning not only in regard to farm production, but to the legal and formal aspects of farm transfer.</p>	
<p>6 HOW CAN YOUNG PEOPLE BE ATTRACTED TO WORK ON FARMS?</p> <p>Attracting young people to work in agriculture requires not only more outreach and flexibility from farms, but government investments into rural areas lacking in social services and decent infrastructure.</p>	

- Issue date: 02/06/2020
- Available at SURE-Farm website

<https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/D3.7-Business-Brief-Infographic.pdf>

9 GIF on policy options for resilience enhancing farm demographics (D3.9)

- Issue date: 01/07/2020
- Available at SURE-Farm website:
 - <https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/GIF-D3.9.Farm-demographics.gif>

- 10 GIF to support the policy brief with a critical analysis of how current policies constrain/enable resilient EU agriculture (D4.6)

THE CAP POST 2020

The CAP needs to change significantly to better support the three resilience capacities of Europe's farming systems: **Robustness, adaptability and transformability**

Support adaptability, by providing direction, in particular through the remuneration of public goods, by increasing flexibility and variability through reducing red tape, and by closing the gap between reflection/innovation and practice.

Different farming systems need different mixes of resilience capacities.

 Transformability

Issue date: 01/08/2020

Available at SURE-Farm website:

- o <https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/GIF-D4.6-CAP-post2020.mp4>

11 Infographic to support the Policy Brief on principles for a resilience-enabling environment (D6.3)

Issue date: 15/02/2021

Available at SURE-Farm website:

- o <https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/D6.3-Infographic.pdf>

12 Infographic to support the policy brief on resilience of farming systems in the EU under current conditions and future scenarios (D5.7)

Issue date: 01/03/2021

Available at SURE-Farm website:

- o <https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/D5.7-Policy-Brief-Infographic.pdf>

13 Final video. SURE-Farm take-home messages

Issue date: 18/05/2021

Available at:

- o SURE-Farm website: <https://www.surefarmproject.eu/digital-materials/>
- o YouTube account: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wqmHI5eeJY>

14 Final infographic: Key findings and recommendations to turn European farming systems more resilient and sustainable.

Issue date: 28/05/2021

Available at SURE-Farm website:

<https://www.surefarmproject.eu/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Infographic-SURE-Farm-Take-home-messages.pdf>